

Integrated Centralized Lab System

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Pakistan is a developing country and number of private/public sector universities are increasing as the young generation is moving towards higher education. Pakistan Engineering Council and Higher Education Commission (HEC) are two highest authorities responsible for the accreditation of degree awarding institutions. Mostly rejections in institute aggradations is not having proper labs. Mostly private sector have labs but lack of government funded projects, while public sector have funding but lack of well equipped labs or professional staff.

Few years back Offices of Research, Innovation and Commercialization (ORIC) department was started in all the universities in Pakistan but except few universities ORIC seems to be a complete failure. One main reason of ORIC failure is lacking of full time staff. ORIC fails in developing International Standards in Research & Development.

Research & Development demands for high standard research in collaboration with universities and industry. Single university research without industry collaboration cant meet high standards. But for Industry collaboration research we need well equipped labs which can cost high to any university. Secondly for such equipments we need highly trained staff too. Research supervisors must be industry experienced people.

One of the best solution can be INTEGRATED CENTERLIZED LAB OR RESEARCH INSTITUTE. Such centers should be formed in all the big cities. In order to make clear understanding we can take an example of Multan city which is considered as biggest education hub in South Punjab. Currently 8 Independent degree awarding universities are registered in which 4 are public sector and 4 private universities .But non of these universities can claim fully well equipped labs in the field of science & technology. How can a researcher work in a limited facility environment? Research is a limitless field. There should be a centralized lab center in a city and all the high standard and well equipped science & technology labs should be setup in that center. Funding should come from all the public & private universities working in city.

Universities will get well equipped labs in half the investment that they need for establishing an individual lab. On the other hand if any university already have a well equipped lab for any science & technology subject then other lab by paying certain Currently such centers are and SINGAPORE. Highly in those centers and that the universities using the utilizing skilled staff.

Establishing such center opportunities to all the universities to contribute lab facilities. All research applied through integrated World is moving towards and we should also organizations and stop

Hurdles in Pakistan Research & Development

- (1) Lack of high standard labs.
- (2) Lack of skilled staff in Public & Private sector University Labs.
- (3) Restricted & complicated research grant procedures in public sector.
- (4) Lack of Industry experienced professionals in research labs.
- (5) Hiring separate staff for ORIC office

universities can use the amount of fee. working in US, CHINA skilled staff will be hired staff can help all centralized. So it is also

can provide equal students in different in research by utilizing grants can also be centralized centers.

such centralized systems start establishing such reinventing the wheel.

If you have a vision or and idea that can help transform our current research & development system then write to us and we can share your idea in Future Vision next edition.

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